

An Improved Application of the Photosensitive 3-Nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl Polyethylene Glycol Support in the Liquid Phase Method of Peptide Synthesis

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The photosensitive 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl polyethylene glycol support was prepared for use in the liquid phase method (LPM) of peptide synthesis by coupling the polymer with 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl chloride instead of coupling with 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoic acid which raised the yield of coupling from 60 to 85.8%. The produced photosensitive polymer was esterified with potassium salts of different Boc amino acids using 18-crown-6, as catalyst in different time, temperatures, molar ratios of reactants and solvents. Preliminary results using 20 equivalents each of 18-crown-6, the potassium salt of Boc amino acid and 0.5 equivalent of the polymer at reaction time 18 h resulted in virtually complete esterification in DMF.

These modifications in the synthesis of the photosensitive polymer support and in its esterification reaction with the 1st Boc amino acid avoid side reactions and raise the yield of the final peptide

Results and Discussions

THE liquid phase method of peptide synthesis using soluble polyethylene glycol was introduced by Bayer *et al.*^{1,2}. Since then, several biologically active peptides have been synthesised using this method. It offers many advantages over classical and solid phase methods of peptide synthesis. However, its major disadvantage has been the low yield of final peptide obtained under such drastic conditions as saponification and hydrazinolysis³⁻⁵, and the incomplete esterification between the COOH terminal of the first amino acid and the polymer.

To accelerate and simplify the removal of the protected peptide acid from the resin, a photosensitive anchoring group was attached to the polyethylene glycol⁶ by esterification of the polymer with 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoic acid. The removal of the final peptide from the produced photosensitive polymer is accomplished by photolysis reaction at 3500 Å under conditions which neither decompose the aromatic amino acid nor cleave the acid or base labile protecting group. The cleave reaction proceeds to 98% within 24 h. To achieve complete attaching of the photosensitive anchoring group to the polymer we used 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl chloride instead of 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoic acid. This modification raised the yield of coupling from 60 to 85.8%. The next step in the peptide synthesis by the liquid phase method involves the esterification of the photosensitive polymer with an N-protected amino acid. Complete reaction of bromomethyl group (complete esterification) is usually desirable in order to avoid any side reactions which decrease the yield of final peptide.

In the present investigation 18-crown-6 was used to catalyse the esterification reaction of 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl polyethylene glycol with the potassium salts of Boc amino acids because of its ability to bind cations⁷ which often allow the corresponding anionic components to function as improved nucleophile⁸. Potassium salts of Boc amino acids were used instead of Cs salts⁹ because they have higher association constants with the crown ethers that are readily available^{10,11}.

The esterification reaction of the above mentioned photosensitive polymer with potassium salts of different Boc amino acid was carried out in different solvents, times molar ratios of the reactants and temperatures to determine the optimum condition for quantitative esterification and the best solvent for this reaction.

The results are summarised in Tables 1-5.

TABLE 1—COMPARISON BETWEEN THE PERCENT INCORPORATION OF Boc AMINO ACID POTASSIUM SALTS INTO 3-NITRO-4-BROMOMETHYLBENZYL POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOMETHYL ETHER WITH 18-CROWN-6 AND WITHOUT IT*

Amino acid	% without 18-crown-6	% with 18-crown-6
Trp	78	98.0
Asn	53	96.5
Pro	85	96.3
Val	88	96.3
Ala	82	95.8
Gly	79	95.5
Tyr (OBZL)	68	79.2

*Reaction conditions: Ratio of equivalent, polymer-18-crown-6-Boc A.A. (0.5:1:1); Solvent - DMF; Temp. = 50°; Time = 48 h.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING THE SOLVENT ON THE PERCENT INCORPORATION OF Boc-ASN AND Boc-ALA POTASSIUM SALTS INTO 3-NITRO-4-BROMOMETHYLBENZOYL POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOMETHYL ETHER*

Solvent	% of reaction in case of Boc-Asn	% of reaction in case of Boc-Ala
DMF	86.9	95.80
CH ₂ Cl ₂	67.5	76.60
Benzene	48.3	38.30
Dioxane	38.6	38.30
Ethanol	29.0	19.16

*Reaction conditions : Ratio of equivalents, polymer - 18-crown-6 - Boc. A.A. (0.5 : 1 : 1); Time = 18 h, Temp. = room temperature.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING TEMPERATURE ON THE PERCENTAGE OF REACTION OF Boc-ASN AND Boc-ALA POTASSIUM SALTS WITH 3-NITRO-4-BROMOMETHYLBENZOYL POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOMETHYL ETHER*

Temp.** °C	% of reaction in case of Boc-Asn	% of reaction in case of Boc-Ala
RT	86.9	95.8
50	96.5	95.8
70	100	100

*Reaction conditions : Ratio of equivalents, polymer - 18-crown-6 - Boc A.A. (0.5 : 1 : 1); solvent = DMF; Time = 18 h.

**RT = Room temperature.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING THE EQUIVALENT RATIOS OF Boc AMINO ACID POTASSIUM SALTS AND 18-CROWN-6 ON THE PERCENTAGE OF REACTION OF Boc-ASN AND Boc-ALA WITH 3-NITRO-4-BROMOMETHYLBENZOYL POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOMETHYL ETHER*

Equivalents		% of reaction in case of Boc-Asn	% of reaction in case of Boc-Ala
18-crown-6	K-salt		
1	1	86.9	95.8
1	2	77.2	76.6
2	1	95.5	57.5
2	2	100.0	100.0

*Reaction conditions : Concn. of polymer = 0.5 mM; Time = 18 h; Temp. = room temperature; Solvent = DMF.

The results shown in Tables 1–5 indicate that 18-crown-6 functions as a suitable catalyst for quantitative esterification between K-salts of Boc amino acids and 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl polyethylene glycol monomethyl ether under mild condition. DMF is considered as the best solvent for this reaction.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF TIME ON THE REACTION OF Boc-ASN AND Boc-ALA POTASSIUM SALTS WITH 3-NITRO-4-BROMOMETHYLBENZOYL POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL MONOMETHYL ETHER*

Time (h)	% of reaction in case of Boc-Asn	% of reaction in case of Boc-Ala
18	86.9	95.8
48	86.9	95.8
72	96.5	100.0

*Reaction conditions : Ratio of equivalents, polymer - 18-crown-6 - Boc A.A. (0.5 : 1 : 1); Temp = room temperature; Solvent = DMF.

Experimental

Synthesis of Boc amino acids were carried out using the reported¹⁰ method. The K-salts of Boc amino acids were synthesised according to the procedure described in literature¹¹. Synthesis of 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoyl chloride was carried out by refluxing (26 g, 0.1 mol) 3-nitro-4-bromomethylbenzoic acid (17.85 g, 0.15 mol) with thionyl chloride at 80° for 6 h. While stirring the excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation in a water-bath at 80° and the product was washed by petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80), (85.8%) (Found : Cl, 12.42. Calcd. for : Cl, 12.42%).

References

- M. MUTTER, H. HGENMAIR and E. BAYER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1971, 83, 883.
- E. BAYER and M. MUTTER, *Nature (London)*, 1972, 237, 512.
- W. GÖHRING and G. JUNG, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1975, 1765.
- M. MUTTER, R. UHMANN and E. BAYER, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1975, 901.
- G. JUNG, G. BOVERMANN, W. GÖHRING and G. HEUSSEL in "Peptides: Chemistry Structure and Biology", eds. R. WALTER and J. MEINHOFER, Ann Arbor Sci. Publ., Ann Arbor, 1975, p. 433.
- F. TJOENG, W. STAINES, S. ST. PIERRE and R. HODGES, *Biochim Biophys. Acta*, 1977, 489.
- C. LIOTTA, H. HARRIS, M. MCCERMOTT, T. GONZALEZ and K. SMITH, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 2417.
- M. YONEIS, S. ABDEL RAHMAN and A. HATTABA, *Indian J. Chem.*, communicated (mss. no. 000).
- B. GISIN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 56, 1476.
- E. SCHNABEL, *Ann. Chem.*, 1967, 702, 188.
- ROSEY and P. GESELLCHEN, *Tetrahedron*, 1976, 38, 3369.